

* Pubmed search for “(model* OR simulation* OR theory OR theoretical OR mathematical) AND (coevolution* OR co-evolution* OR coevolve* OR co-evolve* OR (red AND queen)) AND (host* OR parasite* OR pathogen*) AND (“2000”[Date - Publication] : “2017”[Date - Publication])”.